

Integrating marine protected areas and spatial fisheries restrictions in ecosystem models of the Aegean Sea

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ABSTRACT

The Mediterranean Sea faces significant ecological challenges, including overexploitation and climate change, that necessitate innovative management strategies. Marine Protected Areas (MPAs) serve as critical management measures in preserving biodiversity and rebuilding fish stocks. This study employed the ECOSPACE modelling framework to assess the impacts of various spatio-temporal management scenarios in the Aegean Sea, focusing on biomass, catches, and spatial distributions of marine populations. The reference scenario revealed a 6 % decline in total biomass and substantial decreases in commercially important species by 2050. While prey species at lower trophic levels showed biomass increases due to reduced predation, these gains were inconsistent across functional groups (FGs). Five scenarios explored MPA placement, extended protection within Natura 2000 areas, and offshore wind farm (OWF) integration. Results demonstrated localized biomass increases within restricted zones but highlighted trade-offs, including effort redistribution and reduced total catches in some cases. Larger MPAs with stricter protections yielded more pronounced ecological benefits, particularly for demersal and benthic species, but posed economic challenges for fisheries. Among the tested scenarios, Scenario 3, which extended the bottom trawling and purse seining restriction area, demonstrated the highest biomass gains for key commercial species with moderate trade-offs in catch, making it suitable for fisheries-focused management. In contrast, Scenarios 1 and 2, which prohibited fisheries within Natura 2000 areas, offered broader conservation benefits, supporting their use in biodiversity-driven strategies. Once in operation, the areas associated with OWFs provided modest conservation benefits, supporting the potential for multi-use marine spatial planning. The findings of the present work can provide valuable insights for policymakers, aiding the development of adaptive management plans that balance biodiversity conservation with sustainable fisheries in the Aegean Sea. Future improvements should integrate high-resolution spatial data and socioeconomic analyses for a holistic understanding.

1. Introduction

The Mediterranean Sea has undergone significant overexploitation, leading to changes in the structure and function of its ecosystems (Lotze et al., 2011) and a decline in the status of most commercial fish and invertebrate stocks (Tsikliras et al. 2015; Colloca et al. 2017). Overfishing is further exacerbated by other human activities, including habitat degradation (Claudet and Fraschetti 2010), pollution (Danovaro 2003), climate change (Lejeune et al. 2010), and the introduction or

expansion of non-indigenous species (Katsanevakis et al. 2016). To manage fish stocks, technical measures such as regulating the fishing effort through spatio-temporal restrictions are necessary (Dunn et al. 2011; Bellido et al. 2020). These controls limit fishing activities in specific areas or during certain seasons, helping to protect fish populations.

Marine ecosystem protection has become a key focus in international legislation and commissions. Within the European Union (EU), several multinational legislative acts have been implemented to regulate and

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safeguard the marine environment (Rodriguez-Perez et al. 2023). The Habitats (EC 1992) and Birds (EC 2009) Directives address both terrestrial and marine conservation goals, with efforts directed towards establishing the Natura 2000 network. This network aims to protect species listed in the annexes of these directives by promoting connectivity and including zones where human activities are restricted (Mazaris et al. 2017). In the marine context, the Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD) was introduced to protect marine ecosystems and achieve a good environmental status by 2030 (EC 2008). The MSFD also advocates for the creation of marine safe havens in conjunction with Natura 2000 areas (Fenberg et al. 2017). In parallel, the Maritime Spatial Planning Directive (MSPD; EC 2014) provides a legal framework to support integrated spatial planning of maritime activities such as fisheries, conservation, and offshore renewable energy, helping balance environmental and socio-economic objectives.

As part of the European Green Deal, the EU adopted the Biodiversity Strategy for 2030 to halt biodiversity loss and promote ecosystem recovery (Hermoso et al. 2022). To support these goals, the European Commission (EC) introduced the 2023 Action Plan to Protect and Restore Marine Ecosystems (EC 2023). The plan targets the designation of at least 30 % of EU marine waters as protected areas, with 10 % under strict protection. It also calls for stronger spatial management measures, such as restricting bottom trawling in sensitive habitats, to enhance ecosystem resilience, rebuild fish stocks, and support sustainable, climate-resilient fisheries across European seas.

Marine Protected Areas (MPAs) are useful in this regard, offering means to conserve habitats and biodiversity while aiding in the recovery of overexploited stocks (Sarker et al. 2023). MPAs, which can range from strict no-take zones to areas allowing sustainable resource use, provide safe havens where depleted populations can rebuild, and habitats can recover (Tuck and Possingham 2000; Nalmpanti et al. 2022). Despite challenges like ocean warming, pollution, and invasive species, MPAs contribute to climate change mitigation by enhancing the resilience of marine ecosystems, aiding carbon sequestration (Duarte de Paula Costa et al. 2023), and supporting coastal protection (Gronrud-Colvert et al. 2021). Similarly, Fisheries Restricted Areas (FRAs) contribute to the recovery of specific exploited stocks and support biodiversity and habitat conservation (Panzeri et al. 2024). In the Aegean Sea, both Greek and Turkish legislation regarding spatio-temporal restrictions on fishing activities is notably complex, involving numerous regulations (Petza et al. 2019). Many FRAs have been established, primarily under fisheries laws, but also through archaeological and maritime legislation. Consequently, identifying and mapping these national FRAs is a challenging task. Although the legislative framework for spatio-temporal fishing restrictions in the Aegean Sea remains complex and sometimes fragmented, efforts to identify and map these restrictions have been carried out for both Greece (Petza et al. 2017) and Türkiye (Dereli et al. 2022).

In addition to MPAs and FRAs, the concept of Other Effective area-based Conservation Measures (OECMs) has gained increasing attention in international conservation policy. Recognized under Aichi Target 11 of the Convention on Biological Diversity in 2010, and defined eight years later (CBD 2018), OECMs are areas not formally designated as protected areas but that nonetheless contribute to in-situ biodiversity conservation (Shabtay et al. 2019). Unlike MPAs, which are established with conservation as their primary objective, OECMs may indirectly achieve conservation outcomes as a result of other management goals (Fitzsimons et al. 2024). Human uses such as offshore renewable energy development (IUCN 2019) and aquaculture (Mascorda Cabre et al. 2021) may function as OECMs in supporting biodiversity objectives when adequately managed. These types of interventions are increasingly relevant in spatial planning contexts, including scenarios that assess conservation benefits from multi-use areas.

The Ecosystem-Based Fisheries Management (EBFM) is a useful management approach that considers the interactions among all biotic ecosystem components, as well as abiotic and anthropogenic drivers of ecosystem dynamics (Pikitch et al. 2004; Morrison et al. 2024). The goal

is to improve current management frameworks through evaluations that integrate ecological, environmental, and socioeconomic dimensions. Ecosystem analyses are particularly valuable for understanding the multilevel impacts of fishing and informing strategic management decisions (Collie et al. 2016). Over the past few decades, food web models of aquatic ecosystems have become more prevalent in the scientific literature, many utilizing the ECOPATH with ECOSIM (EwE) modelling approach (Polovina 1984; Christensen and Walters 2004). EwE is a widely used tool for analyzing exploited aquatic ecosystems that supports the implementation of EBFM (Keramidas et al. 2023). Within the EwE framework, ECOSPACE is a module designed to model the 2D dynamics of trophic web components in space and time (Walters et al. 1999). This tool has been utilized in Europe to quantify the spatio-temporal effects of fisheries on marine species, evaluate the impacts of various management scenarios, such as the implementation of MPAs, develop spatial optimization routines, and assess the effects of climate change on marine ecosystems (Keramidas et al. 2023). On a Mediterranean level, ECOSPACE models have been developed in the eastern (Israeli coast: Ofir et al. 2023; Thermaikos Gulf: Dimarchopoulou et al. 2024), central (Adriatic Sea: Fouzai et al. 2012; Gulf of Gabès: Abdou et al. 2016; Halouani et al. 2016; Abdou et al. 2020), and western (Catalan Sea: Coll et al. 2016; Pennino et al. 2020) parts of the basin, as well as for its entire surface area (Piroddi et al. 2022).

The main objective of this study was to develop a spatio-temporal model for the Aegean Sea to evaluate how environmental conditions and fishing activities, as recorded during a historical calibration period, influence the biomass, catches, and spatial distribution of marine populations over time. Specifically, the evaluation of various MPA scenarios aimed to examine how different allocation and characteristics of MPAs affect biomass and commercial fisheries yields within the ecosystem. The model was used to assess relative differences among spatial protection scenarios under constant environmental conditions after 2021, rather than to forecast absolute future states. Model findings can guide the implementation of marine spatial planning directives at both regional and Mediterranean scales. In particular, the tested scenarios directly evaluated measures proposed under the recent Action Plan, alongside broader objectives of the MSFD and the Biodiversity Strategy 2030. By assessing alternative MPA placements and gear-specific fishing restrictions, the model offered practical insights to support adaptive management strategies that balance conservation goals with the sustainable use of marine resources.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Study area

The Aegean Sea (Division 37.3.1 of FAO Major Area 37; Geographical Subarea, GSA 22), including the area of Crete (GSA 23), is bordered by two countries, Greece and Türkiye (Fig. 1). Commercial fisheries in the European part of the Aegean Sea are governed by the EU's Common Fisheries Policy (CFP), national laws and regional regulations; recreational fisheries primarily fall under national competence (Keramidas et al. 2018). Fisheries in Greece are governed by a combination of frameworks, including binding regulations from the General Fisheries Commission for the Mediterranean (GFCM), relevant EU legislation, and national legal instruments. In Türkiye, the Fishing Notification is the main regulatory control mechanism for fisheries, while the most recent notification (Notification 5/1) adopted on 1 September 2020, is active for four years (Dereli et al. 2022). According to the Network of Managers of Marine Protected Areas in the Mediterranean Sea (MedPAN), only two officially established MPAs in the Aegean Sea qualify as fully protected areas, defined by the simultaneous application of no-go, no-take, and no-fishing measures: the National Marine Park of Alonissos Northern Sporades (NMPANS) in Greece and the Special Environmental Protection Area in Gökova Bay, Türkiye. NMPANS has two primary protected zones (A and B). In Zone A1 (Piperi Island), the core of the marine park,

Fig. 1. The Aegean Sea modelled area (light blue color), including the isobath layers (light gray lines), of the ECOPATH model (defined in Keramidas et al. 2022) and the ECOSPACE simulations.

the approach of any vessel within 3 nautical miles (NM) of the coast is prohibited. Zones A2-A9 are generally strictly protected, while Zone B has no specific spatial regulations regarding fisheries. On the other hand, six areas in Gökova Bay have been declared as no-fishing zones to preserve diversity and rebuild marine populations. Beyond the established protected areas, the Natura 2000 network serves as the primary conservation mechanism in both the Greek territorial and international waters of the Aegean Sea. A total of 186 Natura 2000 sites with a marine component have been officially characterised in the most recent review (EEA 2024), encompassing 2.3 % of the marine surface area. New areas are added every year.

2.2. Pre-existing ECOPATH and ECOSIM models of the Aegean Sea

The ECOPATH base model was created to depict the food web of the Aegean Sea, structured with 44 functional groups (FGs) to represent the average state of the ecosystem from 2003 to 2006, and featuring four commercial fleets namely bottom trawlers (OTB), purse seiners (PS), beach seiners (BS) and small-scale coastal vessels (SSC). An in-depth description of the ECOPATH modelling approach, including the species composition of FGs, input data, parametrization, and results, is available in Keramidas et al. (2022). This model was then extended to include temporal variability using ECOSIM, incorporating time series data of biomass, commercial catches (landings-discards), fishing effort, and environmental parameters. The ECOSIM model was calibrated with observed data from 2006 to 2021, while forecast scenarios were simulated until 2050, to assess fisheries, climate change, and combined impacts. The sensitivity of ECOSIM model outputs to various degrees of uncertainty in ECOPATH input parameters was assessed using Monte Carlo simulations. For more information regarding the ECOSIM parameterization, calibration, fine-tuning, and simulation results, the

reader may refer to Keramidas et al. (2024). The temporal dynamics of the model in this study were based on the previously established ECOSIM framework, using the same calibration period (2006–2021) and forecast period (2022–2050).

2.3. ECOSPACE parameterization and input data

ECOSPACE is the spatial and temporal dynamic module of the Ewe software, building upon the mass-balanced ECOPATH model and the time-dynamic simulations of ECOSIM (Walters et al. 1999). For the Aegean Sea application, the ECOSPACE model (Ewe v6.6.8) was initialized using the ECOPATH input data (Keramidas et al. 2022) and the ECOSIM-calibrated time series (Keramidas et al. 2024). The spatial domain was represented by a raster grid of 262 rows and 257 columns, with each cell measuring $0.025^\circ \times 0.025^\circ$ in latitude–longitude resolution, approximately 2.8 km (1.5 NM) per side. The total modelled area spanned approximately 201,500 km² (Keramidas et al. 2022), comprising 67,334 cells, of which 35,876 were designated as the study area, while the remainder were excluded (land or non-target water bodies) (Fig. 2). Each spatial cell was categorized as either land or water and assigned a specific habitat type, based on five benthic substrate classes derived from the European Marine Observation and Data Network (EMODnet): mud, sand, seagrass meadows (e.g., *Posidonia oceanica*), coarse and mixed sediments, and rocky bottoms. The underlying bathymetry data were extracted from the General Bathymetric Chart of the Oceans (GEBCO) using a bounding box defined by the geographic coordinates $41^\circ 7' 30''$ N to $34^\circ 40' 52''$ N and $22^\circ 23' 46''$ E to $28^\circ 38' 6''$ E.

Environmental layers for net primary production (PP) and sea surface temperature (SST) were obtained from the Copernicus Marine Environmental Monitoring Service (CMEMS) biogeochemical validated

Fig. 2. The base map of the Aegean Sea illustrating the spatial distribution of environmental parameters and benthic habitats used in the ECOSPACE model. Grey areas represent land, while white regions denote water cells that were not part of the study area. For environmental parameters that vary over time, the displayed layer represents conditions for the initial year of the model (2006).

model (MEDSEA_REANALYSIS_BIO_006_008), averaged annually between 2003 and 2006. These layers were extended temporally through 2021 using the spatio-temporal data framework (STDF) (Steenbeek et al. 2013), enabling dynamic spatial interactions between environmental parameters and FG distributions during model simulations. For the forecast period (2022–2050), no future climate forcing was applied. Instead, environmental forcing was kept constant using the average values from the final five years of the calibration period (2017–2021). As a result, the model simulations from 2022 onward reflect equilibrium dynamics under stable environmental conditions. Within ECOSPACE, the biomass pools representing the FGs were distributed across this spatial grid and were allowed to move among cells based on a “Eulerian” approach, where movement is modelled as biomass flow between adjacent cells, without tracking individual histories (Walters et al. 1999). The distribution of FGs across the grid was driven by habitat assignment, environmental preferences, dispersal rates, and foraging behavior. Although the Aegean Sea is an open ecosystem, species migration across model boundaries was not considered due to insufficient data. As such, net organism inputs or outputs to and from the study area were excluded from the simulation (Halouani et al. 2020).

In each cell, biomass and consumption rates of the FGs were dynamically calculated through the trophic interactions governed by the differential equations from EwE (Walters et al. 2000). Fishing fleets were spatially distributed and linked to relevant habitats and accessibility rules. In ECOSPACE, fishing mortality is distributed across the spatial grid based on the relative profitability of each cell, which depends on local biomass availability, catchability, and market value (Romagnoni et al. 2015). This dynamic allocation allowed the model to simulate

effort displacement in response to changing resource conditions. It should be noted that the modelled effort distribution may differ from observed patterns, as it does not incorporate real-world constraints. The Natura 2000 network was integrated as an additional spatial layer, including only the marine sites established within Greek and international waters, as Turkish sites have not yet been formally included in the network. These areas covered 5.1 % of the study area (1809 cells) and were used for the spatial allocation of protection scenarios.

2.4. Spatial preferences and environmental responses

In ECOSPACE, the spatial distribution of groups and species is regulated by several key parameters, like base dispersal rate, relative dispersal in bad habitat, relative vulnerability to predation in bad habitat, and relative feeding rate in bad habitat modules (Supplementary Table S1). These parameters have default values but can also be adjusted for each group individually. The base dispersal rate (km/year), which corresponds to swimming speed, has a default value of 300 and a range from zero to infinity. The dispersal rates suggested by Christensen and Walters (2024) were utilized for most FGs, categorized into three levels: 300 km/year for highly mobile pelagic species, 30 km/year for demersal species, and 3 km/year for non-dispersing species (Supplementary Table S1). ECOSPACE assumes that species perform worse in non-favourable habitats compared to favourable ones. This was modelled using three parameters that function as weight factors. The relative dispersal in bad habitat parameter increases the dispersal rate in unfavourable habitats, simulating an increased effort to move to better conditions. It can range from 1 (disabling the mechanism) to 10, with a

Table 1

Detailed description of the reference scenario (Sc0), assuming business-as-usual conditions: spatial fisheries restrictions including the percent area covered and temporal restrictions for each fishing gear, according to the Greek and Turkish legislation for the Aegean Sea. The table includes only the spatial restrictions that could be integrated into the software, considering specific limitations regarding cell size.

Fishing gear	Spatial restrictions	Restricted area	Temporal restrictions	
			Greece	Türkiye
OTB	Bottom trawling is prohibited within 1.5 NM from the coast (permanent-all year) (Supplementary Figure S1)	8.90 %	Bottom trawling is prohibited in all areas (GSA 22 and GSA 23):	Bottom trawling is prohibited in all areas (GSA 22):
	Bottom trawling is prohibited at depths beyond 1000 m (permanent-all year) (Supplementary Figure S1)	11.27 %	24 May-30 Sep	15 Apr-31 Aug
	Bottom trawling is prohibited within 3 NM from the coast or within the 50 m isobath where depth is reached in shorter distance from shore, and over seabeds with marine vegetation, especially <i>Posidonia oceanica</i> (permanent-all year)	0.57 %	24-31 Dec	in international waters (beyond 6 NM from the coast) and west of 25th meridian of GSA 22:
	Bottom trawling is prohibited in defined gulfs and bays, in all zones of the National Marine Park of Alonissos Northern Sporades, and in 6 zones of the Special Environmental Protection Area in Gökova Bay (permanent-all year)		in selected gulfs and bays:	15 Jul-31 Aug
	Bottom trawling is prohibited in selected gulfs and bays (seasonal) (Supplementary Figure S2)	1.13 %	1 May-31 Oct	
Bottom trawling is prohibited within 6 NM from the coast in GSA 22 and 23 and west of the 25th meridian of GSA 22 (seasonal) (Supplementary Figure S3)	35.09 %	in international waters (beyond 6 NM from the coast) and west of 25th meridian of GSA 22:		
			16 Jul-30 Sep	
PS	Purse seining during the day is prohibited deeper than the 30 m isobath in Greece, while during the night it is prohibited shallower than the 50 m isobath for Greece and the 24 m isobath for Türkiye. Night seining is also prohibited over seabeds with marine vegetation, especially <i>Posidonia oceanica</i> (permanent-all year) (Supplementary Figure S4)	1.69 %	Purse seining is prohibited in all areas (GSA 22 and GSA 23):	Purse seining is prohibited in all areas (GSA 22):
	Purse seining is prohibited within 3 NM from the coast in Zone A1 (Piperi Island) of the National Marine Park of Alonissos Northern Sporades, and in 6 zones of the Special Environmental Protection Area in Gökova Bay (permanent-all year)	0.07 %	15 Dec-28 Feb (for night seines)	15 Apr-31 Aug
	Purse seining is prohibited within 1.5 NM from the coast in Zones A2-A9 and B1 of the National Marine Park of Alonissos Northern Sporades (permanent-all year)	0.10 %	1 Jul-31 Aug (for day seines)	
BS	Beach seining is prohibited in defined gulfs and bays, in all zones of the National Marine Park of Alonissos Northern Sporades, and over seabeds with marine vegetation, especially <i>Posidonia oceanica</i> (permanent-all year) (Supplementary Figure S5)	1.22 %	Beach seining is prohibited in all areas (GSA 22 and GSA 23):	Beach seining is not an official fishing gear in Türkiye
SSC	Small-scale coastal fishing is prohibited within 3 NM from the coast in Zone A1 (Piperi Island) of the National Marine Park of Alonissos Northern Sporades, and in 6 zones of the Special Environmental Protection Area in Gökova Bay (permanent-all year)	0.07 %	Small-scale coastal fishing is allowed all year with temporal restrictions being implemented for specific gears	

default value of 2, indicating twice the speed in non-favourable habitats compared to favourable ones (Walters 2000). Relative vulnerability to predation in bad habitat is a weight factor for the vulnerability parameter in ECOSIM, reflecting increased vulnerability to predation (or decreased sheltering capacity) in suboptimal habitats. It can be set between 1 and 100, with a default value of 2, meaning twice as vulnerable in unfavourable conditions (Walters 2000). Finally, relative feeding rate in bad habitat determines the feeding activity and subsequent growth of a group in an unfavourable habitat. It reduces the feeding rate, thereby lowering the consumption/biomass ratio (Q/B) from ECOPATH. This parameter can be adjusted within a range from 0 to 1, with a default setting of 0.05. In this study, the parameter values were adjusted according to the trophic levels of the FGs (Fouzai et al. 2012): 0.95 for primary producers, since photosynthesis is unaffected by habitat type; 0.01 for species at intermediate trophic levels ($TL = 2.00-3.49$); 0.3 for species at medium-high trophic levels ($TL = 3.50-3.99$); and 0.6 for species at higher trophic levels ($TL > 4.00$).

ECOSPACE employs a habitat preference approach to dynamically allocate ECOSIM biomass across a grid of cells on a base map, distinguishing between preferred and non-preferred habitats. The biomass distribution was determined by the foraging capacity of each FG within a cell. FGs exhibited higher feeding and survival rates in cells with preferred habitats, allowing for greater growth. The computed foraging capacity was adjusted based on cell-specific habitat foraging usage and/or environmental capacities through foraging responses (Christensen

et al. 2014). Additionally, ECOSPACE can derive foraging capacity from FGs affinities for specific habitats and their functional responses to environmental conditions. Habitat capacity was based on the habitat layers, such as sediment type, with each habitat type assigned a suitability proportion for each FG, within a range from 0 to 1 (Supplementary Table S2).

Environmental capacity was determined by the environmental driver maps, while environmental foraging responses were integrated for 35 FGs with available data from AquaMaps (Kaschner et al. 2019), for depth and SST. Although AquaMaps uses trapezoidal-shaped response functions for each species, the Aegean Sea model adopted a Gaussian-based shape for environmental effects, aligning with approaches used in other studies (Ofir et al. 2023; Dimarchopoulou et al. 2024). Environmental preferences, including minimum, maximum, and the 10th and 90th percentile values, were obtained from AquaMaps (Kaschner et al. 2019). The midpoint of the tolerance range for each parameter was calculated as the average of the 10th and 90th percentiles for each species. In the model, these preferences were incorporated into the response function for each environmental parameter by using the interdecile ranges (the difference between the first and the ninth deciles) as the left and right standard deviations, resulting in composite Gaussian-based responses with tailored ranges for each group (Supplementary Tables S3 and S4). For multi-species FGs, environmental parameters were determined by weighting them according to the biomass contribution of individual species. In this study, foraging capacity was

integrated using the preferences of all available FGs for both habitat and environmental responses.

2.5. Reference simulation and validation

The four fishing fleets of the ECOPATH model were integrated into ECOSPACE, with fishing zones designated based on habitat type. Following the current legislative measures in the simulations, bottom trawlers were not allowed to fish over seagrass meadows and rocky substrates, while purse seiners and beach seiners were not allowed to fish over seagrass meadows. All fishing operations in the model were assumed to comply with legal regulations and spatio-temporal restrictions, although this is not always the case in reality (Dereli et al. 2022). The reference ECOSPACE simulation (Sc0) ran until 2050 and included the current legislation measures of the Aegean Sea (business-as-usual) regarding protected areas for each gear type (Table 1). Permanent and seasonal MPAs for each gear were defined using the enforcement module of the software and the STDF, which set both their temporal framework (regarding seasonal allowance) and the spatio-temporal framework (including the year in which each MPA was implemented) (Table 1). Most spatial restrictions targeted bottom trawlers, while a permanent trawling ban within 1.5 NM from the coast (covering 8.90 % of the study area) was applied to most areas, with some sites having bans at 2 or 3 NM, according to the legislation. Additionally, a seasonal trawling ban within 6 NM and west of the 25th meridian of GSA 22 (an extra 35.09 % of the study area) was enforced from October to June. Regarding purse seiners, for technical reasons, the model did not consider the permanent restriction within 300 m of the coast (i.e., 11 % of the cell's length), thus using only the 30-meter isobath for Greece and the 24-meter isobath for Türkiye as fishing limits. Also, the regulation which prohibits fishing in depths <70 % of the net's total vertical height was not enforced since the model could not parameterise specific net dimensions and different heights. Spatial restrictions for small-scale coastal vessels covered the smallest protected area percentage, as they lacked specific legislative measures for all gears, with the exception of the NMPANS.

Model validation ensured that predictions of species distribution and ecological impacts were reliable and applicable to real-world scenarios

Table 2

Detailed description of the five MPA scenarios tested. Hypothetical fisheries restrictions according to the MSFD and the Biodiversity Strategy 2030, the actual and suggested sites of offshore windfarms (OWF), and the percentages of the protected area by gear are presented. Each scenario was tested under the condition that the current restrictions from Sc0 (BaU) remained in effect.

Scenario	Description	Area protected
Sc0	Business-as-usual fisheries restrictions from Table 1 (Greek and Turkish legislation for the Aegean Sea)	OTB: 20.74 % PS: 1.86 % BS: 1.22 % SSC: 0.07 %
Natura 2000 network		
Sc1	Trawling ban in all Natura 2000 sites (Supplementary Figure S6)	OTB: BaU plus 2.79 %
Sc2	Fishing ban for all gears in all Natura 2000 sites (Supplementary Figure S6)	OTB: BaU plus 2.79 % (23.53 %) PS: BaU plus 4.41 % (6.27 %) BS: BaU plus 4.68 % (5.90 %) SSC: BaU plus 5.02 % (5.09 %)
European Commission (EC) Action Plan spatial restrictions		
Sc3	Trawling ban within the 50 m isobath and purse seining ban within the 70 m isobath (extra 10 % of the study area) (Supplementary Figures S7 and S8)	OTB: BaU plus 2.36 % (23.1 %) PS: BaU plus 6.44 % (8.3 %)
Sc4	Trawling ban within 3 NM from the coast in all areas (30 % of the study area) (Supplementary Figure S9)	OTB: BaU plus 7.82 % (28.56 %)
Marine Spatial Planning (MSP)		
Sc5	Fishing ban for all gears in OWF locations including potential proposed sites (Supplementary Figure S10)	OTB: BaU plus 0.49 % (21.23 %) PS: BaU plus 0.54 % (2.4 %) BS: BaU plus 0.62 % (1.84 %) SSC: BaU plus 0.64 % (0.71 %)

(Stow et al. 2009; Effrosynidis et al. 2020). To assess the predictive accuracy of the ECOSPACE model, we compared modelled biomass outputs with spatially explicit biomass index data from the Mediterranean International Trawl Survey (MEDITS: Spedicato et al. 2019). Specifically, georeferenced abundance data were used for GSAs 22 and 23 for the years 2006 and 2021, corresponding to the starting and ending years of the calibration period of the model. These observed values, obtained from expert-reviewed MEDITS hauls, were averaged across survey stations and compared with modelled biomass distributions for the same years. Since the ECOSIM calibration used averaged, non-georeferenced biomass values, the validation conducted here represents an independent spatial comparison of model predictions. This approach enabled a spatially explicit comparison in selected years by aligning observed survey data with model outputs, establishing a structured framework to assess the congruence between empirical and simulated biomass distributions, necessary for model validation (Püts et al. 2020) and applied in other spatial studies (Barents Sea: Nascimento et al. 2023; Thermaikos Gulf: Dimarchopoulou et al. 2024).

The spatially explicit nature of the simulations also required the use of spatial data analysis techniques to effectively interpret temporal and spatial changes in biomass distribution. In this study, we summarized these changes by calculating the centre of biomass, a spatial analogue to the centre of mass, for each FG at each time step (Woillez et al. 2007). To determine the centre of biomass, we first computed the total biomass along each row and column of the spatial grid for all FGs. These row and column sums were then converted into cumulative distributions. The midpoint (i.e., the value corresponding to 50 % of the cumulative total) was identified for both the rows and columns. The grid cell whose cumulative biomass was closest to this midpoint in each direction was defined as the centre of biomass for that time step. This method provided a robust way to summarize shifts in biomass distribution across the study area, while accounting for both concentrated and dispersed spatial patterns (Friedland et al. 2021). Given the large extent of the study area, biomass for many species was broadly distributed. In cases where high-density biomass patches occurred near the edges or coasts, the centre of biomass remained in the centre due to the influence of the wider, low-density spread across the map (Nascimento et al. 2023).

Fig. 3. ECOSPACE predictions of spatial biomass distribution (in t/km²) for each functional group in the Aegean Sea model under reference scenario Sc0, averaged over the calibration period (2006–2021). The color gradient represents biomass values, and the period corresponds to years with available observed biomass data.

Fig. 4. ECOSPACE predictions of catch spatial distribution (in t/km²) for each functional group in the Aegean Sea model under reference scenario Sc0, averaged over the calibration period (2006–2021). The color gradient represents biomass values, and the period corresponds to years with available observed catch data.

2.6. Spatial fisheries scenarios and MPA management

Five spatio-temporal management scenarios, incorporating hypothetical MPAs that are off-limits to various fishing activities, were analysed for the Aegean Sea, with their detailed descriptions provided in Table 2. These scenarios included bans on different types of fishing gears in Natura 2000 sites, specific percentage protections under the European

Commission’s Action Plan, and offshore wind farm (OWF) placement, with each scenario built upon the existing restrictions of the business-as-usual legislative measures of Sc0. The first two scenarios focused on Natura 2000 areas: in the first scenario (Sc1), a trawling ban was implemented in all sites, while the second scenario (Sc2) established no-take zones for all gears. The third (Sc3) and fourth (Sc4) scenarios simulated the Action Plan’s recommendations by introducing MPA

Fig. 5. Centre of mass analysis of species distribution in the Aegean Sea. The central panel shows the spatial distribution of biomass (grayscale), while the top and right panels display marginal distributions along latitude and longitude. Dashed blue lines indicate the centre of mass coordinates. Black dots represent observed data, while cyan lines show fitted trends.

closures to restrict specific fishing gears, while the fifth scenario (Sc5) prohibited all fishing activity within existing and proposed OWF locations in the Aegean Sea (Table 2). All scenarios were implemented during the forecast period (2022–2050).

3. Results

3.1. Model validation and reference ECOSPACE simulation

The model validation revealed an overall alignment between observed biomass and model projections, particularly for European hake, red mullets, and shrimps, as illustrated in the spatial overlays for 2006 and 2021 (Supplementary Figures S11 and S12). However, discrepancies were evident for FGs like Norway lobster and horse mackerels, where observed hotspots did not always match model predictions. Temporal comparisons between 2006 (starting year of the model) and 2021 (end year of the calibration period) indicated shifts in species distributions, with some maintaining consistent patterns while others showing notable changes.

The spatial distribution of biomass for all FGs is illustrated in Fig. 3, for an average of the calibration period (2006–2021). A distinctive

coastal-to-offshore gradient was observed, with higher biomass concentrations in many FGs in nearshore and mid-shelf areas, likely driven by enhanced productivity. On the other hand, deeper waters and offshore regions generally exhibited lower biomass densities, except for FGs of species with pelagic or migratory behaviours, or species with a broader bathymetry range. The simulated reference scenario (Sc0) without the implementation of extra MPAs demonstrated significant declines in biomass for many ecologically and commercially important species by the end of the simulation period (2050). These declines primarily reflect the cumulative effects of fishing pressure and environmental changes applied during the calibration period, with the model reaching equilibrium under constant environmental conditions thereafter. Overall, total biomass decreased by 10 % relative to the initial period (Supplementary Table S5). Specific declines were observed among FGs, particularly those of commercial importance, such as rockfish (92 %), medium-large demersals 2 (80 %), gurnards (70 %) and sharks (63 %). Demersal and benthic fish groups exhibited higher average decrease in biomass (50 %) compared to pelagic groups (23 %). On the other hand, biomass gains were observed in only 9 of the 44 FGs in the model, including planktivorous deep sea fish (211 %) and flatfishes (170 %), octopus and cuttlefish (28 %) and slope crabs (25 %), due

Fig. 6. Radial plot showing the distance of the centre of mass of each functional group from the coastline. Concentric circles represent distance intervals (20 km), while gray lines connect the origin to each group centre of mass location.

to reduced predation pressures. However, this biomass increase did not consistently lead to higher catches, as many of these groups were of limited market value, except in the case of flatfishes (97 % catch increase), mackerels (14 %), and octopus and cuttlefish (0.9 % catch increase).

The spatial distribution of catch is presented in Fig. 4 for the same yearly average as biomass. Coastal and shelf regions exhibited the highest catch rates, indicating targeted exploitation in areas of high productivity and accessibility. A pronounced north-to-south gradient was also observed, with northern regions showing higher catch rates, especially for commercial FGs. The simulation period showed an overall decrease in catch volumes for most groups, especially intermediate trophic level species, with decreases up to 94 % compared to 2006, with an average decrease of 53 % among FGs (Supplementary Table S5). Most notable catch declines were observed among certain high-demand species, including shrimps, anglerfish, European hake, medium-large demersals 2, red mullets, and horse mackerels, with decreases ranging from 49 % to 86 %.

Regarding the centre of mass, the distribution of biomass in the study area appeared to be uneven, with a clear concentration toward the northern areas (Fig. 5). Additionally, the cross-sectional plots reinforced this observation, as the density values were significantly higher along the horizontal slice through the centre of mass when moving northward. The centre of mass itself was skewed slightly toward the north, further suggesting that the biomass is not evenly spread but is instead more abundant in the northern regions. Over the simulation period, about 85 % of the FGs showed minimal movement, with their centres of mass staying within 20 km of their starting points. A few more mobile groups,

like dolphins and monk seal shifted between 20 and 40 km, while sharks and deep sea fish surpassed the 40 km perimeter (Fig. 6). The displacement likely reflects responses to environmental drivers like temperature rise, productivity gradients, prey availability, and human activities.

3.2. Tested scenarios, MPA implementations and spatial distribution

In scenario Sc1 where bottom trawling was prohibited throughout the Natura 2000 network with an additional protection area of almost 3 %, total biomass remained virtually unchanged in comparison to Sc0 by 2050 (Table 3). However, the biomass of several FGs increased due to the implementation of protective measures. For instance, marginal increases were observed in biomass of medium-large demersals 2 (1.8 %), rays and skates (1.6 %), and small demersals 3 (0.9 %). Conversely, a decrease in biomass was observed in 21 of 44 groups, although minor in most cases, with an average decrease of 1 %. The restriction regime for bottom trawling also led to a slight decrease in total catch, with the most significant declines being observed in commercially important FGs like rays and skates (2 %), red mullets (0.9 %) and gurnards (0.9 %), although a positive impact was observed in the catches of shrimps and European hake which increased by 1.6 % and 1.3 %, respectively. The average catch decrease across all FGs was marginal (0.3 %; Table 3).

The results of scenario Sc2 were similar to Sc1 in terms of exhibited biomass increases or decreases in most FGs. The largest additional percentage of protection in Natura 2000 areas was established for small-scale coastal fisheries (5 %). Biomass increases were particularly notable in groups targeted by both trawling and small-scale fisheries,

Table 3

Variations in biomass and catch estimates for all functional groups for the five tested scenarios in relation to the basic scenario (Sc0). Changes are expressed in percentage (where negative values indicate a decrease) and computed for the final year of simulation (2050). The color gradient represents increasing (shades of green) and decreasing (shades of yellow) ratios. Results are rounded to two decimal places; consequently, minor differences (< 0.001) between scenarios are not numerically distinguishable.

	Biomass					Catch				
	Sc1	Sc2	Sc3	Sc4	Sc5	Sc1	Sc2	Sc3	Sc4	Sc5
1. Phytoplankton	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00					
2. Micro/Mesozooplankton	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00					
3. Macrozooplankton	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.01	0.00					
4. Benthic invertebrates	-0.04	-0.40	-0.24	0.02	-0.06	0.00	-4.14	-0.13	-0.04	-1.08
5. Polychaetes	-0.02	0.01	0.00	-0.04	0.02					
6. Benthic small crustaceans	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00					
7. Jellyfish	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00					
8. Shelf crabs	0.00	-0.12	0.14	-0.01	-0.01	-0.70	-1.73	1.17	-2.45	-0.08
9. Slope crabs	0.10	0.25	0.01	0.30	0.03					
10. Shrimps	0.00	-0.04	0.00	-0.01	0.00	1.58	1.59	2.34	4.07	-0.11
11. Lobsters	0.01	-0.93	0.07	-0.07	-0.04	-0.04	0.68	-0.28	-0.23	0.65
12. Norway lobster	0.20	0.31	0.50	0.38	0.05	0.99	1.01	1.63	2.96	-0.17
13. Octopus and cuttlefish	0.00	-0.10	-0.09	0.07	0.00	-0.50	0.00	-0.90	-0.91	0.34
14. Squids	0.00	-0.05	0.03	0.01	0.00	0.17	0.26	2.12	0.79	0.02
15. European anchovy	-0.01	-0.07	0.09	-0.01	0.00	-0.05	-0.55	6.68	-0.13	0.06
16. European pilchard	-0.03	0.03	0.41	0.00	0.02	-0.20	-1.98	-48.79	-0.25	-0.10
17. Other small pelagics	-0.01	0.10	0.28	-0.01	0.01	0.02	-2.14	-3.87	-0.04	0.04
18. Picarels and bogue	-0.05	-0.22	0.09	0.04	-0.03	-0.38	-1.00	-1.08	-1.41	0.13
19. Mackerels	-0.03	-0.23	8.00	0.08	-0.10	-0.16	0.85	-10.13	-0.22	0.27
20. Horse mackerels	0.08	0.20	-0.26	0.01	0.01	-0.35	-0.29	6.76	0.40	0.02
21. Medium pelagics	0.00	0.05	-0.30	0.06	0.00	-0.11	-0.11	2.68	-0.47	0.21
22. Large pelagics	0.03	0.21	-1.29	0.08	0.04	-0.01	-0.19	0.61	0.02	-0.08
23. Anglerfish	-0.03	-0.10	-0.18	-0.06	0.00	0.79	0.92	1.95	2.75	-0.11
24. Flatfishes	-0.08	-0.01	0.10	-0.13	0.05	-0.18	-1.39	0.01	-0.55	-0.05
25. European hake	0.00	-0.05	0.02	0.01	0.00	0.72	1.24	1.70	1.89	-0.13
26. Other gadiforms	-0.06	-0.13	-0.09	-0.13	0.00	1.29	1.24	2.34	3.61	-0.25
27. Gurnards	0.02	-0.32	-0.06	0.06	0.01	-0.89	-1.71	0.81	-2.73	0.11
28. Red mullets	0.16	0.32	-0.14	0.50	0.06	-0.93	-1.76	0.49	-3.18	0.05
29. Rockfish	0.42	4.26	-0.12	0.81	0.03	-0.07	-4.04	0.38	-0.20	-0.61
30. Small demersals 1	-0.02	-0.31	-0.04	-0.03	-0.02	-0.32	-0.93	0.37	-1.45	0.10
31. Small demersals 2	-0.01	0.02	0.35	-0.01	0.01	-0.34	-1.03	0.84	-1.54	0.18
32. Small demersals 3	0.92	15.29	-0.52	3.96	0.46	0.25	-4.40	0.49	2.18	-0.83
33. Medium-large demersals 1	-0.02	-0.34	0.78	0.01	-0.02	-0.23	-0.95	1.34	-1.00	0.13
34. Medium-large demersals 2	1.77	46.28	7.19	0.80	4.49	0.92	2.88	6.23	0.79	3.41
35. Planktivorous deep sea fish	-0.02	-0.01	-0.02	-0.03	0.00	1.21	1.14	2.16	2.94	0.30
36. Piscivorous deep sea fish	0.00	-0.01	-0.03	-0.04	0.00	1.24	1.13	2.40	4.06	-0.04
37. Rays and skates	1.59	0.22	7.26	0.29	-0.47	-1.98	-3.23	-5.92	-2.21	0.09
38. Sharks	-0.03	-0.61	-0.39	-0.04	-0.09	-0.03	0.07	1.02	0.08	0.07
39. Sea turtles	-0.53	-1.90	-1.23	-1.52	0.18	-0.28	-0.84	-1.33	-1.32	0.55
40. Seabirds	0.14	0.30	-0.39	0.58	0.05	-0.02	3.13	-0.29	-0.16	0.49
41. Dolphins	-0.01	-0.07	0.10	-0.04	-0.01	-0.07	3.12	0.11	-0.15	0.39
42. Monk seal	0.02	0.09	-0.04	0.01	0.01	-0.05	2.81	-0.38	-0.10	0.38
43. Discards	0.05	-0.18	-0.78	0.48	0.03					
44. Detritus	0.00	0.02	0.01	0.00	0.00					
Total	0.00	-0.01	0.02	0.00	0.00	-0.06	-0.57	-4.52	-0.09	0.09
Average Increase	0.24	3.40	1.11	0.32	0.21	0.76	1.38	1.94	2.04	0.36
Average Decrease	-0.05	-0.27	-0.30	-0.13	-0.05	-0.34	-1.71	-6.65	-0.94	-0.28

Fig. 7. ECOSPACE predictions of spatial biomass distribution for benthic, demersal, pelagic, fish, and invertebrate functional groups in the Aegean Sea model for each tested scenario (Sc1-Sc5), compared to reference scenario Sc0 for the end of the simulation period (2050). The ratios (measured in t/km^2) indicate relative biomass differences, where a value of 1 signifies identical biomass levels between the tested scenarios and Sc0, and values lower or higher than 1 represent decreased or increased biomass in the tested scenarios relative to Sc0, respectively.

like medium-large demersals 2 (46 %), small demersals 3 (16 %), and rockfish (4.3 %). Increases were also observed in pelagic groups, targeted by purse seiners, such as horse mackerels (0.2 %) and European pilchard (0.1 %). Differences between the two scenarios were observed in lobsters, for which a biomass increase was observed in Sc1 but a decrease was observed in Sc2, while the opposite pattern was observed for European pilchard and small demersals 2. Total catch was 0.6 % lower compared to Sc0, but increases were observed in the catches of more FGs compared to Sc1, with the largest increases observed in medium-large demersals 2 (2.9 %) and shrimps (1.6 %).

In Sc3, bottom trawling was prohibited below the 50 m isobath and purse seining was prohibited below the 70 m isobath, resulting in an additional 10 % of protected area in the Aegean Sea. By the end of the simulation period in 2050, biomass increases were observed in benthic FGs targeted by bottom trawlers, like rays and skates (6.2 %) and shrimps (2.3 %). Simultaneously, biomass gains were observed in pelagic groups due to the reduced area of operation for purse seiners, including horse mackerels (6.8 %) and European anchovy (6.7 %) (Table 3). Regarding catch, a total decrease of 4.5 % was recorded, the largest among all scenarios tested. The catches of demersal FGs demonstrated an average decrease of 1.8 %, while pelagic groups experienced a greater decrease (16 %) compared to Sc0 in 2050 (Table 3). The biomass increase in groups like medium-large demersals 2 and small demersals 2 also impacted their catches, which increased by 6.2 % and 0.8 %, respectively. However, this was not the case for pelagic groups, where catches declined for certain groups, ranging from 1.1 %

for picarels and bogue to 49 % for European pilchard.

In Sc4, the results highlighted less noticeable increases in biomass compared to Sc0, particularly for demersal groups, like small demersal 3, rays and skates, medium-large demersals 2, and Norway lobster (Table 3). However, the average biomass increase was smaller compared to Sc3, as the pelagic compartment of the food web remained relatively unaffected. The total catch, on the other hand, experienced a slight decrease (0.1 %) by the end of the simulation period. Nonetheless, the average decrease among FGs was smaller in Sc4 (0.9 %) compared to Sc3 (6.6 %). This may be explained by the fact that, although the protected area was larger in Sc4, it did not significantly affect FGs targeted by other fishing gears.

In scenario Sc5, the potential positive or negative effects of OWFs in the Aegean Sea on biomass and catch among FGs were explored. The results of this scenario revealed positive impacts on biomass for most FGs (26 out of 44) as well as on total biomass, highlighting the importance of protecting an area from all fishing fleets. The most significant biomass increase was observed in medium-large demersals 2 (4.5 %), while the biomass for vulnerable and protected groups like sea turtles and monk seal increased (Table 3). The biomass increase in several FGs was mirrored in their catches, with increases recorded in 22 of the 35 FGs with available catches (Table 3).

Maps illustrating the spatial distribution of biomass and catch for benthic, demersal, and pelagic FGs, as well as fish, invertebrate, planktonic, and other FGs, under each tested scenario (Sc1-Sc5) compared to Sc0 are presented for the end of the simulation period in

Fig. 8. ECOSPACE predictions of spatial catch distribution for benthic, demersal, pelagic, fish, and invertebrate functional groups in the Aegean Sea model for each tested scenario (Sc1-Sc5), compared to reference scenario Sc0 for the end of the simulation period (2050). The ratios (measured in t/km^2) indicate relative catch differences, where a value of 1 signifies identical catch levels between the tested scenarios and Sc0, and values lower or higher than 1 represent decreased or increased catch in the tested scenarios relative to Sc0, respectively.

2050 in Figs. 7 and 8. Regarding biomass, the simulations generally indicated a projected increase (blue-shaded areas) within the zones where fishing restrictions were implemented, in all scenarios. On the other hand, regarding catches, an opposite pattern was observed in the aforementioned areas. In Sc2, where fishing activities were restricted in Natura 2000 areas for all gears, increased commercial catches were predicted along the boundaries of the restricted zones and in the remaining open areas overall, especially for pelagic and invertebrate FGs.

4. Discussion

4.1. Reference ECOSPACE model

This study highlighted the influence of MPAs and fishing restrictions on species biomass and catch dynamics in the Aegean Sea within a spatio-temporal framework. The reference scenario (Sc0), which did not include additional MPAs, revealed substantial declines in biomass and

catches for many ecologically and commercially significant species by 2050. Overall biomass decreased by 10 %, with considerable reductions observed especially in demersal groups. These trends are consistent with previous studies that underscore the vulnerability of marine ecosystems to overfishing and environmental stressors. For instance, in Catalan Sea the combined effects of fishing and environmental changes had synergistic or antagonistic impacts on species like hake, anchovy, and sardine, leading to marked declines in biomass (Coll et al. 2016), while in the Gulf of Gabès, bottom trawling has contributed significantly to ecosystem degradation and overexploitation of several stocks (Abdou et al. 2020).

Model validation indicated a generally good alignment between observed and predicted biomass distributions, particularly for European hake, red mullets, and shrimps. This confirmed that the spatial dynamics of key FGs were realistically captured. However, mismatches for other groups, such as Norway lobster and horse mackerels, suggested that some environmental variability or fishing dynamics might not be fully represented. Still, incorporating these environmental and fishing

parameters improved overall spatial prediction, especially for groups with well-defined habitat preferences. Also, the movement of the majority of FGs likely reflected the responses to key environmental drivers, such as productivity gradients, shifts in prey distribution, and changing environmental conditions. For highly mobile species, like sharks and dolphins, tracking prey and accessing optimal foraging zones are essential for survival and reproductive success. In the model, several FGs displayed slight northward or offshore shifts in their centre of biomass. This may reflect redistribution toward cooler or more productive waters, particularly in the northern Aegean, where nutrient influx and primary productivity tend to be higher (Kokkos and Sylaios 2016) and can support richer food webs (Worm and Duffy 2003). Additionally, changes in sea temperature may be influencing habitat suitability and driving species northward or toward deeper waters, as indicated by shifts in biomass centroids in the simulations; consistent with observed trends in the eastern Mediterranean (Hattab et al. 2014).

Demersal and benthic groups appeared to be disproportionately affected, experiencing the highest average biomass declines, likely due to the intensive bottom trawling practices targeting these habitats. The adverse impacts of fishing activities on demersal and benthic species are not reported for the first time. For instance, in the northern-central Adriatic Sea, ECOSPACE modelling has shown that the current fishing practices have led to significant declines in key species, such as European hake, sharks, and rays (Fouzai et al. 2012). In the Aegean Sea, European hake, anglerfish, and red mullets are traditional bottom-trawling targets, justifying their decline, especially in the northern part, where the majority of bottom trawling activity occurs (Tserpes et al. 2011). These trends are consistent with independent studies that reveal overexploitation dating back decades. In contrast, prey species like small pelagic fish and invertebrates have become more abundant due to reduced predation pressure, a phenomenon observed in other Mediterranean ecosystems (Prato et al. 2013). Thus, some lower trophic level groups showed biomass increases, which can be attributed to the model computation framework regarding reduced predation pressure (Keramidas et al. 2024). However, this trophic cascade did not consistently translate into higher catches, except for some FGs like flatfishes, which exhibited significant catch increases. This pattern aligns with the broader understanding of how fishing-induced changes in predator-prey dynamics can lead to shifts in ecosystem structure (Akoglu 2023).

Nevertheless, the overall decrease in catch volumes, especially among high-demand species such as anglerfish and European hake, raised concerns about the sustainability of current fishing practices and existing management measures. Their decline could threaten the sustainability of these stocks and trigger trophic imbalances, such as increased abundance of smaller prey species and reduced top-down control in the food web, highlighting the cascading effects of predator depletion on marine food webs (Heymans et al. 2014). Existing management measures in the Mediterranean Sea, such as seasonal trawling bans and MPAs, have shown mixed outcomes (Cardinale et al. 2017). While in the Aegean Sea, some studies have reported positive ecological responses, such as biomass increases near MPAs (Dimarchopoulou et al. 2018; Petza et al. 2019), the results of the present study suggested that current efforts may not yet be sufficient to counteract broader ecosystem-level declines. Seasonal closures may offer short-term relief, but their long-term effectiveness remains uncertain, especially when followed by intense fishing activity. While recent studies highlighted the value of spatial and temporal protection measures (Dimarchopoulou et al. 2024), further targeted evaluation is needed to assess the isolated impact of seasonal bans. Moreover, weak enforcement and non-compliance undermine the effectiveness of these regulations, as is the case in many Mediterranean fisheries (Iacarella et al. 2021).

4.2. ECOSPACE scenarios and MPA placement

Despite the challenges, MPAs are widely recognized as a promising

management measure for safeguarding marine biodiversity and promoting the recovery of overexploited stocks (Di Franco et al. 2016). Scenarios Sc1 and Sc2, which introduced varying levels of fishing restrictions within the Natura 2000 network, led to biomass increases for certain groups, like rays and skates, and medium-large demersals 2. These findings demonstrated the potential of targeted protection measures to benefit vulnerable species. However, the limited overall impact on total biomass and catches indicated that the scale and spatial distribution of protection are critical for achieving meaningful ecological recovery. Similar conclusions have been drawn in other Mediterranean studies, where insufficiently large or poorly enforced MPAs failed to deliver significant conservation outcomes (Agardy et al. 2011). Notably, Sc2 which involved broader fishing restrictions, did not consistently outperform Sc1 in terms of biomass recovery. For instance, European hake exhibited a biomass increase in Sc1 but not in Sc2, likely due to redistributed fishing effort intensifying in areas where the species remained vulnerable (Cabral et al. 2017). These scenarios had a conservation-focused approach, across multiple FGs, by enforcing gear bans in Natura 2000 areas, although with slightly lower total catches.

In areas with high predator abundance, like the already protected Natura 2000 areas, the protection offered by MPAs can lead to trophic cascades, where prey populations decline due to increased predation (Prato et al. 2013). These interactions underscore the complexity of marine ecosystems and the need for nuanced management strategies. For example, models suggest that larger MPAs with smaller perimeter-to-surface ratios are more effective at reducing concentrated fishing pressure near their boundaries (Halpern and Warner 2003), a phenomenon known as the “fishing-the-line” effect (Kelner et al. 2007). When a spatial closure is implemented, ECOSPACE models are based on redistributing fishing effort in the remaining fished areas, instead of reducing the total effort (de Mutsert et al. 2024). As a result, when fishing effort is redistributed to areas adjacent to MPAs, it may compromise some of the ecological gains achieved. This outcome reflects a realistic trade-off, indicating the importance of carefully selecting MPA locations; ideally in areas that reduce negative impacts from displaced effort while maximizing conservation benefits (Rees et al. 2021). Similar insights have emerged from studies in other heavily exploited regions in the Mediterranean, such as the Gulf of Gabès (Abdou et al. 2016) and Thermaikos Gulf (Dimarchopoulou et al. 2024).

Scenarios Sc3 and Sc4, which expanded protected areas and imposed more strict fishing restrictions on medium-scale fleets, showed more pronounced biomass increases, particularly for benthic and demersal groups like medium-large demersals 2, and rays and skates. These findings are consistent with theoretical models that predict greater ecological benefits with larger MPAs, as they encompass more critical habitats and reduce overall fishing mortality (Gronud-Colvert et al. 2021). However, the reduction in total catches, especially for pelagic species in Sc3, underscored the trade-offs between conservation goals and fisheries productivity (Andersen et al. 2015). While MPAs can lead to biomass increases for commercially important species, they may also result in short-term reductions in total catch, creating economic challenges for fishers (Sumaila et al. 2000). These trade-offs are particularly pronounced in ecosystems like the Aegean Sea, where fishing pressure is already high (Tsikliras et al. 2013). The slightly smaller biomass increases in Sc4 compared to Sc3, despite the larger protected area, suggest that the pelagic compartment of the ecosystem may require alternative management measures. This could include strategies beyond spatial protections alone, like seasonal closures or gear modifications to reduce impacts on these highly mobile species.

On the other hand, reductions in overall fishing effort are critical to achieving sustainable outcomes, especially in regions like the Mediterranean, where most stocks are not managed by quotas (Keramidas et al. 2024). For example, seasonal bans aligned with spawning periods or targeted restrictions on non-selective fishing gear can yield substantial benefits for both commercial and vulnerable species (Karr et al. 2021). Also, the spillover benefits of MPAs should be considered, where

increased biomass within protected areas spills into adjacent unprotected zones, enhancing catches and profitability. Such dynamics highlight the potential for MPAs to balance conservation and economic objectives if designed and implemented effectively (Halouani et al. 2016). Based on changes in biomass and catch for key commercial FGs (e.g., medium-large demersals 2, European anchovy, and shrimps), Sc3 emerged as the most favorable for fisheries-focused management. Furthermore, these scenarios directly addressed the objectives outlined in the EC Action Plan, which promotes spatial fisheries management measures, stricter gear regulations, and expanded marine protected areas. The model findings supported the Action Plan's goals by demonstrating that well-designed MPAs and targeted fishing restrictions can enhance ecosystem resilience while minimizing socioeconomic disruption.

The inclusion of OWFs as closed to fishing areas (equivalent to small-scale MPAs) in Sc5 revealed positive impacts on biomass for several FGs, including medium-large demersals 2 and Norway lobster. Given that fishing activities are not allowed in the areas where OWFs are installed, their contribution to the food web was assessed through biomass responses. Additionally, since the additional OWF closed to fishing area did not exceed 1 % for any of the four fleets, they were practically treated as OECMs. These results demonstrated the potential for renewable energy infrastructure to support marine conservation, primarily through localized increases in functional group biomass. However, the relatively limited spatial footprint of OWFs means their standalone benefits are modest. This finding is consistent with studies in other systems (e.g., Bay of Seine: Halouani et al. 2020; Noguès et al. 2022), which have shown that while OWFs can provide localized refuges for marine life, they are most effective when integrated into broader conservation strategies. However, it is important to reiterate that OWFs were treated here as small, protected areas, thus focusing on their potential conservation benefits post-construction while disregarding any impacts resulting from their construction and operation phase. This simplification excludes the potential ecological disturbances caused during their development (Stranddorf et al. 2024).

Indeed, the construction phase of OWFs can have significant impacts on marine life, particularly for benthic habitats and species, as the installation of fixed structures on the seabed often involves drilling, pile-driving, and other disruptive activities (Cones et al. 2022; Jézéquel et al. 2022). On the other hand, floating offshore wind farms (FOWFs) might reduce many of the construction-related impacts associated with fixed installations, particularly by avoiding pile driving and large-scale foundation disturbance (Maxwell et al. 2022). However, their anchoring systems can still cause localized seafloor impacts, including abrasion, scouring, and sediment resuspension from mooring lines and cables (Maxwell et al. 2022; Danovaro et al. 2024). Given the ecological sensitivity, high biodiversity, and slower water renewal rates of the Mediterranean Sea, the deployment of any type of OWFs in this region must be approached with particular caution compared to other basins like the North Sea. Planning should follow ecosystem-based management principles to avoid cumulative environmental pressures (Lloret et al. 2022).

The spatial analysis highlighted that biomass increases were consistently observed within restricted zones across all scenarios, affirming the localized benefits of MPAs. Demersal species showed more spatial variability, with some declines in the nearshore zones and stability or increases in offshore regions, suggesting a redistribution of biomass under different scenarios. Given the large spatial extent of the study area, identifying clear or substantial biomass changes in regions outside fisheries restrictions is challenging. The results suggested that most detectable increases were spatially concentrated within or near protected zones, while changes elsewhere were limited in both extent and magnitude. Also, the redistribution of fishing effort to adjacent areas raises concerns about localized overexploitation, a phenomenon documented in global MPA studies (Agardy et al. 2011). The observed increases in commercial catches near MPA boundaries suggest potential

benefits from "edge effects," where spillover enhances fisheries productivity in adjacent areas (Ohayon et al. 2021).

4.3. Limitations and future improvements

Despite their utility, spatio-temporal models like ECOSPACE have inherent limitations that must be considered when interpreting results (Steenbeek et al. 2020). These models rely heavily on underlying data and assumptions, including species distribution patterns, habitat preferences, and trophic interactions. In this model, benthic habitat data were obtained from EMODnet in vector format. While the ECOSPACE framework allows for the proportional assignment of multiple habitat types per spatial cell, the original data did not provide habitat composition at a resolution finer than the cell level. As such, each cell was assigned to the dominant habitat type based on highest coverage. This may have led to an underrepresentation of less dominant habitats, particularly in areas where habitat boundaries intersected with cell edges, although such cases were relatively infrequent and the overall degree of underrepresentation was minimal. To account for habitat-related species responses, the Habitat Foraging Capacity (HFC) approach was implemented, which defines a continuous relative habitat capacity for each FG, allowing species to utilize each spatial cell based on a suitability ratio derived from multiple environmental variables (Christensen et al. 2014). As a result, species can move dynamically across habitats in response to shifting conditions, improving spatial realism in the simulations (Coll et al. 2019).

In other cases, data limitations introduce uncertainties that affect the accuracy of quantitative predictions. For example, highly migratory species, such as large pelagic fish, are often poorly represented in these models due to their complex movement patterns and seasonal presence (Hervann et al. 2020). ECOSPACE tends to perform better for spatially bound FGs, such as demersal species, than for fast-moving pelagic groups, whose distributions are often influenced by large-scale environmental factors and are more challenging to capture accurately. To improve the spatial fit, future applications should prioritize high-resolution data and carefully select FGs with sufficient empirical coverage. In the Aegean Sea, the variability observed in model performance for different FGs further highlighted the importance of data quality and coverage. Additionally, the evaluation of ecosystem models can benefit from the application of multi-criteria validation approaches that consider not only species-specific outputs but also broader ecological indicators, spatial patterns, and uncertainty analyses (Donati et al. 2024).

Future advancements in ecosystem modelling should aim to address these limitations by integrating high-resolution spatial and temporal data, refining habitat-specific parameters, and incorporating comprehensive socioeconomic analyses. For MPAs to be effective, they must be strategically located in areas that maximize ecological benefits while minimizing socioeconomic disruptions (Dimarchopoulou et al. 2018). Incorporating buffer zones around core protected areas could further enhance ecological connectivity and mitigate the pressure from adjacent fishing activities (Kirkman 2013). Large MPAs with minimal adjacency to heavily fished areas, combined with reductions in overall fishing effort, represent a promising approach to achieving sustainable fisheries management. In conclusion, spatio-temporal ecosystem models like ECOSPACE provide valuable insights into the complex interactions between ecological and spatial factors in marine fisheries management. The results of the tested scenarios of this study can enable policymakers to evaluate the potential outcomes of different strategies and design adaptive management plans that balance biodiversity conservation with the needs of fishing communities. While the establishment of MPAs and other spatial protections is a necessary step toward rebuilding marine ecosystems, their success depends on complementary measures, such as fishing effort reductions and targeted gear restrictions. Future studies may expand on this framework by incorporating climate change scenarios to assess and predict how shifting environmental drivers might

interact with spatial protection measures.

5. Conclusions

This study underscored the importance of spatially explicit ecosystem models like ECOSPACE in informing sustainable fisheries management and marine conservation strategies. Results highlighted the significant ecological challenges in the Aegean Sea due to over-exploitation and environmental stressors. Reference projections indicated substantial declines in biomass and catches for many key species during the forecast period, reflecting cumulative impacts from fishing and environmental variability during the calibration period (2006–2021) and equilibrium dynamics under fixed conditions thereafter. Scenarios incorporating expanded MPAs demonstrated localized biomass recovery, particularly for demersal and benthic species, while also revealing the potential for unintended consequences, such as effort displacement and decreased catches in some cases. The findings suggested that larger MPAs with minimal adjacency to heavily fished areas and complementary measures, such as reductions in overall fishing effort and targeted gear restrictions, are critical to achieving sustainable outcomes. Thus, ECOSPACE simulations provide a useful tool for evaluating and refining Action Plan strategies at regional scales, such as the Aegean Sea. These findings highlighted the importance of aligning MPA design with management objectives, whether ecological, economic, or both. However, the results also underscored the limitations of existing models, particularly in capturing the dynamics of highly migratory species and the socio-economic dimensions of fisheries. Future efforts should concentrate on integrating projected environmental changes, refining model inputs, and improving high-resolution spatial data to enhance the realism and utility of ecosystem simulations for management under evolving environmental conditions. By balancing biodiversity conservation with the needs of fishing communities, adaptive management approaches informed by ecosystem models can support the restoration of marine ecosystems and the long-term sustainability of fisheries in the Aegean Sea and beyond.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Ioannis Keramidas: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Methodology, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Donna Dimarchopoulou:** Writing – review & editing, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Nikolaos Kokkos:** Visualization, Methodology, Data curation. **Tushith Islam:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Ghasan Halouani:** Validation, Methodology, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Georgios Sylaios:** Writing – review & editing, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Data curation. **Athanassios C. Tsikliras:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Data curation, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Supplementary materials

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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